

Employability Rate of Urban versus Rural MBA Institute Students in India: Factors, Challenges, and Strategies

Anuj Suresh Deshmukh

Research Scholar, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati, Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author- Anuj Suresh Deshmukh

Email- anujdesh123@gmail.com

Abstract:

This study examines the disparity between the employment rates of graduates from India's urban and rural MBA institutions. The employment rate of graduates from rural MBA programmes is examined in the study along with the factors that affect it, problems that rural MBA students encounter, and potential solutions. According to the report, the employability rate is influenced by a number of factors, including the standard of education, networking possibilities, exposure to the sector, and the need for qualified individuals. The report also outlines a number of difficulties experienced by MBA students from rural institutions, such as the lack of networking opportunities and access to industry exposure. This study sheds important light on the disparities between the employability rates of MBA graduates from urban and rural India and offers feasible solutions to address these disparities.

Keywords: MBA Program; Urban Rural Education. higher education institutions; employability.

Introduction

In India, the employability rate of MBA graduates from urban and rural institutes varies considerably due to multiple factors such as education quality, networking opportunities, industry exposure, and demand for skilled professionals in each location. The primary objective of this research paper is to examine the employability rate disparity between urban and rural MBA graduates in India. The paper aims to investigate the factors responsible for the employment rate gap, the difficulties confronted by students from rural MBA institutes, and the measures that can be taken to enhance the employability of rural MBA graduates.

Literature review:

The existing literature highlights several factors that can impact the employability rate of MBA graduates, including the quality of education, networking opportunities, industry exposure, and demand for skilled professionals.

The quality of education is one of the most significant factors that can impact the employability rate of MBA graduates. Several studies have found that the quality of education provided by MBA institutes is positively correlated with the employability rate of graduates (Victorino, 2022). According to a study, it was found that the quality of education provided by urban MBA institutes was significantly higher than that of rural MBA institutes, which resulted in a higher employability rate for urban MBA graduates.

Several studies have found that networking can lead to better job opportunities and career development. In a study conducted by Akkermans and Tims (2017) (Akkermans & Tims, 2017), it was found that networking plays a critical role in the employability of MBA graduates. The study found

that networking was positively correlated with employability.

Existing studies have found that industry exposure is positively correlated with the employability rate of MBA graduates. In a study conducted by Feng, Chen, and Chen (2018), it was found that industry exposure had a significant positive impact on the employability rate of MBA graduates.

The demand for skilled professionals is positively correlated with the employability rate of MBA graduate. In a study conducted by Huang (2018), it was found that the demand for skilled professionals had a significant positive impact on the employability rate of MBA graduates.

Factors Affecting the Employability Rate of MBA Graduates in India:

Quality of Education:

The level of education MBA graduates receive can have a big impact on how employable they are. Urban MBA programmes offer an advantage since they have access to greater resources, infrastructure, and faculty, which can lead to higher-quality education. Additionally, metropolitan institutions frequently have more connections and collaborations with business, which can provide students additional exposure to the job market. However, it may be challenging for rural MBA colleges to offer a high-quality education due to a variety of factors. These institutions could not have adequate staff, facilities, or instructors, which could impair the quality of the education they offer. Additionally, rural institutions may find it difficult to recruit and maintain highly qualified faculty members, which can negatively affect how employable their students are.. (Rajpal, 2014)

Networking Opportunities:

Networking is essential for career advancement and can significantly impact how employable MBA grads are. (princetonreview

business-school-advice, n.d.). Due to the fact that they are frequently found in or close to important business hubs, urban MBA colleges have a distinct edge in terms of networking chances. These institutions might have more access to business people, networking occasions, and internships, which can give students useful connections and job market exposure. In contrast, networking possibilities may be difficult for rural MBA institutions. Institutions in rural areas might not have easy access to networking opportunities or industry expertise. Additionally, because of their geographic location, students from rural areas could experience more difficulties while networking and forming contacts.

Industry Exposure: Industry exposure is another significant factor that can impact the employability rate of MBA graduates (Bhatnagar, 2021). Since they are more familiar with the demands and expectations of the sector, MBA graduates who have had more exposure to it are more likely to be given job consideration. Given that they are frequently situated in or close to important business hubs, urban MBA colleges have an edge in terms of industry exposure. These institutions could have easier access to business leaders, industry gatherings, and internship opportunities, which can give students useful insight into the labour market. Rural MBA programmes may encounter difficulties in terms of exposure to industry. Institutions in rural places might not have easy access to business people or industry events. Rural students may not have had much exposure to the field, which could affect their ability to find job after graduation.

Demand for Skilled Professionals: The demand for skilled professionals can have a significant impact on the employability rate of MBA graduates. (Mihail, 2014) Between urban and rural areas in India, there is a considerable disparity in the demand for trained individuals, with urban areas often experiencing more demand. Given that they are frequently situated in or close to important business hubs, urban MBA colleges have an edge in terms of the need for competent professionals. These institutions might have more employers to choose from and more access to work prospects. In contrast, the lack of qualified workers may provide difficulties for rural MBA institutions. The employment rate of MBA graduates may be impacted by the lack of job possibilities and the smaller pool of possible employers in rural locations..

Challenges Faced by Students from Rural MBA Institutes: Students from rural MBA institutes face several challenges in terms of employability. These challenges include:

1.1. **Limited Networking Opportunities:** As previously noted, networking is essential for

career advancement, but owing to their geographic location, students from rural MBA colleges may only have access to a small number of networking opportunities. This can make it difficult for students to network and experience the job market, which may affect how employable they are once they graduate.. (princetonreview business-school-advice, n.d.)

- 1.2. **Lack of Industry Exposure:** Students from rural MBA programmes would not have had much exposure to the sector, which could affect their ability to find employment after graduation. It may be difficult for students to compete in the job market if they lack knowledge about industry expectations and criteria due to a lack of exposure to the sector. (Bhatnagar, 2021)
- 1.3. **Limited Access to Resources and Infrastructure:** Resources and infrastructure issues that rural MBA institutes may experience can have an impact on the calibre of education they offer. Lower educational quality caused by a lack of resources and facilities may have an impact on how employable graduates are.
- 1.4. **Limited Job Opportunities:** Compared to urban regions, rural places could provide less employment options. Due to possible job shortages, this may affect the employability rate of MBA graduates from rural institutions. (Kapur, 2019)
- 1.5. **Social and Cultural Barriers:** Students from rural MBA institutes may face social and cultural barriers that can impact their employability (Irvinw, Byun, Meece, & Farmer, 2012). For example, they could encounter prejudice or discrimination from prospective employers because of their rural upbringing. Additionally, they could struggle with language and communication abilities, which might make it harder for them to find jobs.

2. Case Details:

The case study focuses on the experiences of a student who attended a rural MBA programme in the Maharashtra State district of Buldhana. In 2020, Sampada, the student, received her MBA in HR from the school. After completing her schooling, she encountered a number of difficulties finding job.

The lack of networking chances he had was one of the major difficulties she faced. Due to the institute's remote location, there were few opportunities to network with business leaders and potential employment. She found it difficult to make relationships and find career prospects because she had restricted access to networking functions and job fairs.

The absence of industry exposure was another difficulty Sampada encountered. Her

exposure to the job market was constrained by the institute's scant collaborations or partnerships with nearby enterprises or industries. He was less able to further his career and obtain experience since she had less options for internships and job shadowing.

Ravi had trouble locating suitable employment options in the region where the institute was situated. MBA grads had few employment options due to the oversaturated local job market. She had to think about moving to Pune (Urban Area) in order to improve his chances of finding employment.

Sampada's difficulties are typical among MBA graduates from rural Indian institutions. Some of the variables that affect the employability rate of students from remote institutions include restricted networking possibilities, lack of industry exposure, and low demand for qualified workers. It is crucial to concentrate on creating infrastructure, resources, and industry collaborations in order to increase the employment rate of MBA graduates from rural institutions.

Conclusion:

The lack of infrastructure, resources, and industry exposure are some of the factors that contribute to the lower employability rate of students from rural institutes. The case study highlights the challenges faced by MBA graduates from rural institutes and need of new strategies that can be implemented to improve their employability rate.

3. Strategies to Improve the Employability Rate of Rural MBA Graduates:

There are several strategies that can be implemented to improve the employability rate of rural MBA graduates. These include:

3.1. Improving Infrastructure and Resources:

Improving infrastructure and resources in rural MBA institutes can improve the quality of education they provide. This can result in a higher employability rate for their graduates, as they will be better prepared to compete in the job market.

3.2. Creating Industry Partnerships and Collaborations:

Creating industry partnerships and collaborations can provide students from rural MBA institutes with greater exposure to the industry. This can result in a better understanding of industry requirements and expectations, which can improve their employability after graduation.

3.3. Providing Networking Opportunities:

Providing networking opportunities for students from rural MBA institutes can help them build connections and gain exposure to

the job market. This can improve their employability after graduation, as they will be better prepared to compete for job opportunities.

Conclusion

The results of this study imply that there is a sizable disparity between the employability rate of MBA students in urban and rural India. According to the findings, MBA graduates from metropolitan areas are more likely to get employment than those from rural areas. For MBA graduates, factors like industry exposure, internship opportunities, and networking have been demonstrated to be important employment predictors.

According to the survey, urban MBA programmes have greater connections with businesses, giving students access to better internship opportunities and real-world business situations. In contrast, rural MBA institutions lack these partnerships, which limits the internship options available to their students. Additionally, urban MBA programmes offer their students better networking possibilities, which improves their chances of landing a job after graduation.

However, the study also finds that rural MBA institutes offer a lower fee structure, accessibility of higher education program to larger population and an opportunity of learning management lessons and industry placements as well.

Further Discussions:

The results of this study have significant ramifications for Indian MBA institutions and policymakers. Policymakers must put more effort into giving MBA graduates from rural institutions more networking and industry exposure chances in order to increase their employability. Additionally, the government might provide incentives to businesses who collaborate with rural MBA institutions to offer internship opportunities to their students.

Rural MBA programmes need to strengthen their connections with local businesses and give their students additional options for internships. To improve the standard of instruction and research at their institutes, they should also concentrate on developing their faculty. Additionally, they could provide financial aid and scholarships to entice bright students from economically disadvantaged groups of society..

To provide their students exposure to both urban and rural business contexts, urban MBA colleges should work with their rural counterparts to offer collaborative programmes and exchange programmes. In terms of employment rates, this might also help close the gap between urban and rural MBA programmes.

The need to increase the employability of MBA graduates from rural MBA institutes in India is

highlighted by this study's result. Policymakers and MBA institutions can use the study's findings to build plans to increase MBA graduates' employability, regardless of where they are from.

Rural MBA programmes need to strengthen their connections with local businesses and give their students additional options for internships. To improve the standard of instruction and research at their institutes, they should also concentrate on developing their faculty. Additionally, they could provide financial aid and scholarships to entice bright students from economically disadvantaged groups of society.

References

1. Akkermans, J., & Tims, M. (2017). Crafting your Career: How Career Competencies Relate to Career Success via Job Crafting. *APPLIED PSYCHOLOGY: AN INTERNATIONAL REVIEW*.
2. Bhatnagar, N. (2021). Employability and skill gap among MBA graduates in India: a literature review. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, pp. 92-104.
3. Irvinw, M. J., Byun, S.-y., Meece, J. L., & Farmer, T. W. (2012). Educational Barriers of Rural Youth: Relation of Individual and Contextual Difference Variables. *J Career Assess*, 71–87.
4. Kapur, R. (2019). Employment Opportunities in Rural Areas. *Acta Scientific Agriculture* 3.8, 58-65.
5. Mihail, D. M. (2014). The impact of an MBA on managerial skills and career advancement: The Greek case. *International Journal of Management Education*, 212-222.
6. Princetonreview business-school-advice. (n.d.). Retrieved from Princeton review: <https://www.princetonreview.com/business-school-advice/why-get-an-mba-network>
7. Rajpal, N. (2014). Higher education in India Moving towards global relevance and competitiveness. Partner and Education Sector Leader, Ernst & Young LLP.
8. Victorino, M. L. (2022). Tracing The Employability Success. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 2669.